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Correlation between Teachers' Qualifications and Teaching Performance

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Abstract

The study investigated the extent to which teachers' qualifications relate teacher's performances among faculty members in one of the Universities in Cagayan de Oro. Descriptive design was employed to analyze the profiles of faculty members regarding their positions, length of service, educational qualifications, seminars attended, memberships in professional organizations, and levels of participation in those organizations and to assess the level of teaching performance as evaluated by the dean, chairperson, and students. To determine the relationship between teaching performance and teachers' profile, a correlational design was utilized. Random sampling was used to identify the population from the fourteen (14) colleges, including the Basic Education department, resulting in the selection of sixty-seven (67) faculty members to participate in the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, and Pearson product. All research questions were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that teachers' qualifications have a significant relationship to teaching performance. Based on the findings, it is recommended that the University continuously organize seminars/workshops for faculty members to foster and sustain teacher effectiveness and ensure that faculty members employ and possess the necessary skills and competencies to teach.

Keywords: *teachers' qualifications, performance, and education*

Introduction

The effectiveness of an education system is intrinsically linked to the caliber of its teachers. To build truly outstanding schools, it is imperative to prioritize substantial investments in enhancing teacher quality and development. An education system is only as good as its teachers (UNESCO, 2015). This means that everyone interested in having a successful education system ought to look for ways in which teachers can become better if not the best because the best teachers form the foundation of best schools. Improving teachers' skills and knowledge is one of the most essential investments of time and money in education that national leaders make, thus educational leaders should look into the qualifications of teachers to ensure school success (Day et al., 2020).

Merriam-Webster dictionary defines qualifications as special skills or types of experience or knowledge that make someone suitable to do a particular job or activity. Therefore, teacher's qualification could mean all the skills required of a teacher to teach effectively. Studies revealed that qualification is one of the most important factors in the teaching process (Munna & Kalam, 2021). It is one of the critical factors that drives students' achievement and teachers' performance. Teacher qualifications can go a long way to bring about student success and teachers' performance.

Teaching performance relates to competence in instruction and management of students and materials in the classroom.

In this study, teacher's qualifications tie teachers to some indicators such as educational attainment, seminars attended and conducted, years of teaching experience, active membership in organization, and positions held.

These indicators are central to this study because they act as a compass through which to navigate or explore the review. Therefore, each of them was thoroughly discussed for proper understanding of how they are related to the teaching performance.

The study involved fourteen colleges and three levels of Basic Education, which are elementary, junior high school, and senior high school. The sources of data and information came from a total of sixty-seven participants of whom are chairpersons, coordinators, deans, and faculty members. It employed a survey type of descriptive research. It collected data that were already on ground. The data were analyzed using frequency counts, mean, and Pearson product.

It is significant to distinguish between teacher quality and teaching quality in the context of the current focus on quantifying teacher effectiveness. The study made use of the notion of Blazar and Kraft (2017) [1] which states that teacher quality is a person's collection of personal characteristics, talents, and understandings that they bring to the classroom, as well as their predisposition for specific behaviors.

Based on teacher evaluations and increases in student achievements, research on teacher effectiveness has discovered the following attributes to be important: strong content knowledge in the subject matter to be taught; knowledge of how to teach others in that subject area (content pedagogy), and skill in implementing effective instructional and assessment practices; understanding of learners and their development, including how to support students with learning differences or difficulties, as well as how to support language and content learning for those who are not already proficient in the language of instruction; general abilities to organize and explain ideas as well as to observe and think diagnostically; and adaptive expertise that allows teachers to make judgments about what is likely to work in a given context in response to students' needs.

Teacher quality in the Philippines is defined by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Teachers' improving levels of knowledge, practice, and professional engagement are described in the standards. Simultaneously, the standards allow for instructors' expanding knowledge to be used with greater sophistication across a broader and more complicated spectrum of teaching and learning contexts (DepEd Order No.42, s. 2017).

Qualification is a special skill or type of experience or knowledge that makes someone suitable to do a particular job or activity. Therefore, teachers' qualification is a particular skill or type of experience or knowledge someone possesses to make him or her suitable to teach. Teachers' qualifications could, therefore, mean all the skills a teacher requires to teach effectively (Casian et al., 2021) [2]. Such skills include formal education, experience, training, certificate/licensing, professional development (Aina & Sunday, 2015) [3] participation in professional organizations (Ebede, 2015) [4], and teachers' empowerment (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2014) [5].

Burroughs et al. (2019) [6] were unable to identify consistent relationships between a teacher's level of education in graduate education and their students' achievement. They did not find any significant relationships between advanced degrees and student achievement in any other subject area. Similarly, Nilsen and Gustafsson (2016) [7] postulate that the review of teacher quality research and advanced degrees are generally poor predictors of teacher quality except in certain contexts such as in the secondary context of mathematics. However, there was a study in which data on educational attainment was more specific than a type of degree. This was the study of Hwang and Son (2021) [8], in which findings showed that there was a significantly negative relationship between holding a mathematics degree and mathematics achievement in two separate cohorts of elementary school children. The study of Phuong Uyen et al. (2021) [9] supported this claim that having a bachelor's degree in math and taking graduate-level math education or graduate-level math courses did not correlate with teacher effectiveness.

On the contrary, Saucedo (2017) [10] and Bonney et al. (2015) [11] reported a positive, significant relationship between the percentage of teachers holding a master's degree and reading achievement of elementary and middle school students. In the same manner, Burroughs et al. (2019) [6] with the data used from the United States' Early Childhood Longitudinal Study, found that subject specific graduate degrees in elementary or early-childhood education were positively related to students' reading achievement gains. Harmsen et al. (2018) [12] found that only one teacher's qualification variable at the teacher level was significantly and positively related to reading achievement in first grade, the possession of an elementary education certificate. However, teacher qualifications do not appear to play a role in mathematics achievement at the teacher level, in fact, there is a significant, negative relationship between mathematics achievement and the number of teachers with advanced degrees at that school level.

Teacher experience refers to the number of years that a teacher has worked as a classroom teacher. Many studies showed a positive relationship between teacher experiences and student achievement (Burroughs et al., 2019) [6].

Harmsen et al. (2018) [12] revealed that fifteen or greater years of teaching experience was significantly and positively related to student achievement in three of four grades in the sample. There was also a significant, positive relationship between teachers with between one and seven years of experience and student achievement in grades four and six. However, there was a significant, negative relationship between teacher experience and student achievement among children whose teachers had between 14 years of experience in third through sixth grade.

Irvine (2019) [13] surveyed the relationship between teacher quality and teacher effectiveness by looking at the teachers' professional preparation characteristics. One category examined was teaching experience, which refers to the number of years of teaching. Results showed that the relationship between teacher experience and teacher effectiveness is not significant. A similar finding was found in the study of Kola and Sunday (2015) [14] that the indicator years of experience is positively correlated with students' academic achievement. Inexperienced teachers are typically less efficient than experienced teachers.

Professional development may influence the quality of instruction according to Burroughs et al. (2019) [6], but most researchers found that teachers' professional development experiences showed only limited associations with their effectiveness. Hammond et al. (2020) [15] identified that professional development had moderate effects on teacher practice and some small effects on student achievement when mediated by teacher practice (Burroughs et al., 2019) [6]. The same result was gathered by Irvine (2019) [13] in the study that examined the relationship between teacher quality and teacher effectiveness by looking at the teachers' professional preparation characteristics. The result suggested that attendance at workshops was positively related to effectiveness.

Furthermore, de Vries et al. (2014) [16] revealed that teachers' continuing professional development (CPD) should improve quality and teaching practices, though teachers vary in the extent to which they participate in CPD activities. He added that beliefs influence working and learning, and teachers' beliefs about learning and teaching influence their institutional decisions. Similar findings were found in the study of Kola and Sunday (2015) [14] that the indicator of professional development was positively correlated with students' academic achievement. Professional development is an aspect of teachers' qualifications that is paramount for an effective classroom teacher and enhances teachers' teaching skills.

Teaching is not a solitary profession; it is impossible to operate as a classroom teacher without interacting with one's classmates and coworkers. Teachers' strength is often derived from their relationships with other educational professionals. As a working teacher, it is critical to rely on your peers for advice. Connecting with other teachers through educational networking will benefit one in the field of education.

Membership in professional organizations is critical to the development of competent teachers. Organizations give chances for teachers to develop the characteristics of effective teachers, as well as personalities that are conducive to success in the field of education (Mbulle, 2023) [17]. Teachers gain a wealth of experience in classrooms and with children in general by joining a professional education organization. Moreover, effective learning communities appear to provide significant benefits for professors, according to extensive documentary data. Reduced isolation, a shared goal and cooperation among professors, better curricular integration, and increased satisfaction with their students' learning are all advantages for faculty (Schleifer et al., 2017) [18].

A qualitative investigation reveals a hierarchical ladder with three levels of empowerment among teachers, ranging from restricted to rewarding to change-enhancing empowerment. The level of empowerment appears to be linked to the teachers' leadership positions and their perceptions of those positions (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2014) [19].

On the topic of teacher leadership, Shen et al. (2020) [20] postulate that a well-developed literature base exists and continues to grow; nonetheless, it remains predominantly an academic topic, and despite progress, teacher leadership remains more of a notion than a reality. Teachers are always been leaders, but there is little evidence in public schools that a deliberate, collaborative effort exists to develop and support widespread teacher leadership. Strong school leadership boosts student achievement, especially when combined with a positive school climate that encourages cooperation and risk-taking; teachers and principals both play a role in developing and sharing leadership. Until and unless the concept of teacher leadership is accepted and cultivated, "simply a teacher" will continue to be the dominant mindset in classrooms. Further, Mourão (2018) [21] supported the notion that leadership has an effect on the organization's performance, on the processes of change, on the commitment, satisfaction, and well-being of employees.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to identify which teachers' qualifications could predict teachers' performances among faculty members in a private University in Cagayan de Oro City, SY 2020-2021. Specifically, it aimed to 1) determine the profile of the faculty members in terms of position held, length of service, educational attainment, seminars attended, membership in professional organization, and level of participation in a professional organization, and 2) evaluate the level of teaching performance as evaluated by dean, chairperson, and students; 3) examine the relationship between teaching performance and teachers' profile, and 4) assess how the educational attainment of teachers impacts their teaching performance.

Methodology

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-research research design to profile faculty members—covering aspects like job position, experience, and education—and explore how these profiles associate to teaching performance. While the descriptive part outlines their characteristics, the correlational part determines at possible links, without implying cause and effect.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the randomly selected sixty-seven (67) faculty members of the fourteen (14) colleges and basic education departments in the school year 2020-2021.

Instrument

Data collection was done using a researcher-made tool that focused on gathering details about faculty members, such as their position, years of service, education level, professional development activities, and involvement in professional organizations. This tool was carefully reviewed by experts to validate its accuracy and was pilot tested to confirm its effectiveness. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.82, indicating strong internal consistency in the measurement. The data on teachers' performance as evaluated by students, chairpersons, and deans was collected using the university's Faculty Evaluation Form.

Procedure

The data collection process started by obtaining required permissions from university authorities and the ethics committee to access faculty information and perform evaluations. Faculty members were informed about the study's objectives, emphasizing voluntary participation and the confidentiality of their responses. A researcher-designed questionnaire was then distributed to the 67 selected faculty members, with guidance on completing sections covering demographic information, professional experience, and participation in professional organizations. Furthermore, data on teaching performance, as assessed by students, chairpersons, and deans, was gathered using the university's Faculty Evaluation Form. Once collected, all data were meticulously checked for completeness and accuracy prior to analysis.

Data Analysis

For data analysis, descriptive statistics was used to determine the profile faculty demographics and professional activities, such as calculating frequencies and averages, and evaluate the level of performance. Pearson R correlation was used to examine relationships between faculty profiles and teaching performance and assess how the educational attainment of teachers impacts their teaching

performance. All research questions were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to allow a 5% probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true, ensuring that any identified relationships in the data are likely not due to chance.

Ethical Considerations

The study prioritized ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Faculty received detailed information on objectives and procedures, allowing for informed decisions, and provided written consent with the right to withdraw freely. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained by anonymizing responses and securing data access to authorized personnel only. The study also adhered to institutional ethics guidelines, receiving prior approval from the university's ethics committee to ensure participant welfare and academic integrity.

Results and Discussion

The findings of the study are presented based on the objectives of the study.

Profile of the faculty members

Table 1. *Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Position*

Position	Frequency	Percent
Chair	18	26.87
Coordinator	9	13.43
Others (Not Designated)	5	7.46
Faculty	16	23.88
Dean	3	4.48
PDSA	2	2.99
Guidance Counselors	3	4.48
Clinical Instructor	2	2.99
Rank and File	2	2.99
No Response (Blank)	7	10.45

Table 1.1 shows the distribution of the profile of the faculty members in terms of position, length of service, educational attainment, professional development as to seminars attended, positions and level of participation in professional organization.

As shown in the position, the majority (18 or 26.87%) are chairs, and a few (2 or 2.99%) are PDSA, Clinical Instructors, and Rank and File. The data revealed that most of the respondents are chairs. Mourão (2018) supported the notion that leadership has an effect on the organization's performance, on the processes of change, on the commitment, satisfaction, and well-being of employees. A strong school leadership boosts achievement, especially when combined with a positive school climate that encourages cooperation and risk-taking; teachers and principals both play a role in developing and sharing leadership (Harmsen et al. (2018).

Table 1.2. Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percent
1-5 Years	3	4.48
6-10 Years	14	20.90
11 Years and Above	49	73.13
No Response (Blank)	1	1.49
Total	67	100.0

As can be gleaned in table 1.2, in terms of the length of service, the majority (49 or 73.13%) are within 11 years and above, and a few (3 or 4.48%) within 1-5 years. The data revealed that most of the respondents have served within 11 years and above. This result implied that respondents have served the university for a number of years already and have earned their tenureship. In the study of Kola and Sunday (2015) and Riordan (2014), the indicator years of experience is positively correlated with students' academic achievement. Inexperienced teachers are typically less efficient than experienced teachers.

Table 1.3. *Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
BS Degree Holder	22	32.84
Master's Degree Holder	37	55.22
Doctorate Degree Holder	6	8.96
No Response (Blank)	2	2.99
Total	67	100.0

Table 1.3, illustrates the educational attainment of the faculty members. The majority (37 or 55.22%) are Master's Degree Holder, and a few (6 or 8.96%) are Doctorate Degree Holder. The data revealed that most of the respondents are Master's Degree Holders.

Some scholars believed that higher degrees showed positive correlation with students' academic achievement. The work of Kola and Sunday (2015) reported that there is a significant relationship between degree holders and students' achievement.

Table 1.4. *Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Professional Development as to Seminars Attended*

<i>Seminars Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Not Attended	2	2.99
1-5 Seminars	25	37.31
6-10 Seminars	25	37.31
11 and above	15	22.39
Total	67	100.0

Table 1.4 highlights the professional development as to seminars attended by the faculty members, which shows that the majority (25 or 37.31%) are within 1-5 and 6-10 seminars attended, and more than one-fifth (22.39 are within 11 and above). The data revealed that most of the respondents have attended 10 seminars. This can be attributed to the fact that the university constantly supported the faculty members in terms of professional development.

De Vries et al. (2013) revealed that teachers' continuing professional development (CPD) should improve quality and teaching practices, though teachers vary in the extent to which they participate in CPD activities. He added that beliefs influence working and learning, and teachers' beliefs about learning and teaching influence their institutional decisions. There is a similar finding found in the study of Kola and Sunday (2015) that the indicator professional development is positively correlated with students' academic achievement.

Table 1.5. *Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Positions in Professional Organization*

<i>Positions in Professional Organization</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Members	86	1
Officers	15	2
Total	101	

Table 1.5 presents the positions held in professional organizations, indicating that rank 1 is held by members (frequency = 86), while rank 2 pertains to those serving as officers. These findings indicate that teachers are actively engaged as members of their respective organizations, with some also holding leadership positions.

Table 1.6. *Profile of the Faculty Members in terms of Level of Participation in Professional Organization*

<i>Level of Participation in Professional Organization</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Active	66	1
Inactive	18	2
No Response (Blank)	17	3
Total	101	

As illustrated in Table 1.6, the level of participation in professional organizations indicates that rank 1 is active membership (frequency = 66), while rank 2 reflects inactive membership. These findings suggest that a significant number of teachers are actively engaged in professional organizations, while some may have failed to renew their memberships, resulting in their inactive status.

Members perform as evaluated by students, chairs, and deans

Table 2.1 presents the teachers' performance as evaluated by students, chairs, and deans. As presented, the deans obtained the highest mean (4.61) verbally described as very high. This is followed by the chair with a mean of (4.58) verbally described as very high, and with students with a mean of (4.12) verbally described as high.

Teachers' Performance

Table 2.1. *Teachers' Performance as Evaluated by Students*

<i>Students</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Very High	11	19.30
High	42	73.68
Moderate	4	7.02
Total	57	100.0
Mean (Average) = 4.12 (High)		

Legend: 4.21-5.00 – Very High, 3.41-4.20 – High, 2.61-3.40 – Moderate, 1.81-2.60 – Low, 1.00-1.80 – Very Low

Table 2.1 presents the teacher's performance as evaluated by students. As presented, the data reveals a predominantly positive assessment. Of the 57 students surveyed, the majority rated the performance as "High," with 42 students (73.68%) assigning this rating.

Additionally, 11 students (19.30%) considered the performance "Very High." Only 4 students (7.02%) rated it as "Moderate". The mean score of 4.12 falls within the "High" range (3.41-4.20), indicating that students generally perceive their teachers' performance positively. This means that the majority of students feel satisfied with the quality of instruction they receive, reflecting well on the teachers' effectiveness in the classroom.

Table 2.2. *Teacher's Performance as Evaluated by Chairs*

Chairperson	Frequency	Percent
Very High	33	57.89
High	24	42.11
Total	57	100.0
Mean (Average) = 4.58 (Very High)		

Legend: 4.21-5.00 – Very High, 3.41-4.20 – High, 2.61-3.40 – Moderate, 1.81-2.60 – Low, 1.00-1.80 – Very Low

Table 2.2 presents the evaluation of teachers' performance as assessed by chairpersons. Among the 57 evaluations, a significant majority rated the performance as "Very High," with 33 chairpersons (57.89%) giving this top rating. Additionally, 24 chairpersons (42.11%) rated the performance as "High."

The mean score of 4.58 categorizes the overall assessment within the "Very High" range (4.21-5.00) which shows that chairpersons generally perceive the performance of teachers as exceptional. This positive evaluation suggests that teachers are meeting or exceeding expectations in their roles, reflecting well on their effectiveness and commitment to teaching.

Table 2.3. *Teacher's Performance as Evaluated by Deans*

Deans	Frequency	Percent
Very High	29	50.88
High	28	49.12
Total	57	100.0
Mean (Average) = 4.61 (Very High)		

Legend: 4.21-5.00 – Very High, 3.41-4.20 – High, 2.61-3.40 – Moderate, 1.81-2.60 – Low, 1.00-1.80 – Very Low

Table 2.3 details the evaluation of teachers' performance as assessed by deans. Out of 57 evaluations, 29 deans (50.88%) rated the performance as "Very High," while 28 deans (49.12%) rated it as "High." This distribution indicates a nearly even split between the two highest performance categories, suggesting a strong overall perception of teacher effectiveness.

The mean score of 4.61 places the evaluation within the "Very High" range (4.21-5.00), indicating that deans generally view teachers' performance as outstanding. This positive assessment reflects a high level of confidence in the teachers' abilities and effectiveness in their roles, aligning with the favorable evaluations provided by both students and chairpersons.

Significant difference between the teacher's performance and their profile

Table 3.1. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Position*

Position	Mean	F-Calculated Value	p-value	Degrees of Freedom	F-Critical (Table) Value	Interpretation
Chair	4.63	0.23	0.792	2 / 55	3.01	Not Significant
Coordinator	4.66					
Dean	4.83					
Faculty	4.70					

Table 3.1 evaluates the differences in teachers' performance based on their positions. The mean scores for each role are: Chair (4.63), Coordinator (4.66), Dean (4.83), and Faculty (4.70).

The F-calculated value is 0.23, with a p-value of 0.792, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05. The F-critical value is 3.01. Since the F-calculated value is less than the F-critical value and the p-value is greater than 0.05, there are no significant differences in teacher performance across the various positions. This indicates that performance perceptions are consistent, regardless of the specific role held.

Table 3.2. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Length of Service*

Length of Service	Mean	F-Calculated Value	p-value	Degrees of Freedom	F-Critical (Table) Value	Interpretation
1-5 Years	4.65	0.37	0.695	2 / 55	3.01	Not Significant
6-10 Years	4.78					
11 Years and above	4.66					

Table 3.2 evaluates the differences in teachers' performance based on length of service, with mean scores of 4.65 for 1-5 years, 4.78 for 6-10 years, and 4.66 for 11 years and above. The F-calculated value is 0.37, and the p-value is 0.695, both indicating no significant differences in performance across these groups, as the F-calculated value is less than the F-critical value of 3.01 and the p-value exceeds 0.05. This suggests that teachers' performance perceptions are consistent regardless of their length of service.

Table 3.3. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>F-Calculated Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>F-Critical (Table) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
B.S. Degree Holder	4.69					
Master's Degree Holder	4.87	3.28	0.054	2 / 55	3.01	Significant
Doctorate Degree Holder	4.42					

Table 3.3 analyzes the differences in teachers' performance based on educational attainment, with the following mean scores: B.S. Degree Holder (4.69), Master's Degree Holder (4.87), and Doctorate Degree Holder (4.42). The F-calculated value is 3.28, and the p-value is 0.054, both indicating a significant difference in performance across the groups, as the F-calculated value exceeds the F-critical value of 3.01. This suggests that educational attainment positively influences teachers' performance evaluations, with Master's Degree holders showing the highest perceived performance.

Table 3.4. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Seminars Attended*

<i>Seminars Attended</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>F-Calculated Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>F-Critical (Table) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Not Attended	4.90					
1-5 Seminars	4.59	5.88	0.002	3/54	2.78	Significant
6-10 Seminars	4.45					
11 and above	3.67					

Table 3.4 analyzes the differences in teachers' performance based on the number of seminars attended. The mean scores are as follows: Not Attended (4.90), 1-5 Seminars (4.59), 6-10 Seminars (4.45), and 11 and above (3.67). The F-calculated value is 5.88, with a p-value of 0.002, both indicating a significant difference in performance across the groups, as the F-calculated value exceeds the F-critical value of 2.78.

This suggests that attending seminars positively influences teachers' performance, with the highest evaluations for those who have not attended any seminars. However, performance appears to decline with the number of seminars attended beyond the first few, implying that additional seminars may not contribute positively to performance or may be less relevant.

Table 3.5. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Positions in Professional Organizations*

<i>Positions in Professional Organizations</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>F-Calculated Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>F-Critical (Table) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Officer	4.90					Not Significant
Member	4.59	1.03	0.076	14	1.7613	

Table 3.5 presents teachers' performance based on their positions in professional organizations, showing mean scores of 4.90 for Officers and 4.59 for Members. The F-calculated value is 1.03, with a p-value of 0.076, indicating no significant difference in performance between the two groups. This suggests that the position within the organization does not significantly affect teachers' perceived performance.

Table 3.6. *Test of Significant Difference between the Teacher's Performance by their Level of Participation in Professional Organizations*

<i>Level of Participation in Professional Organizations</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>F-Calculated Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>F-Critical (Table) Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Active	4.90	5.83	0.009	17	1.7396	Significant
Inactive	4.59					

Table 3.6 analyzes the differences in teachers' performance based on their level of participation in professional organizations. Active participants have a mean score of 4.90, while Inactive participants have a mean score of 4.59. The F-calculated value is 5.83, with a p-value of 0.009, indicating a significant difference in performance between the two groups. This suggests that active involvement in professional organizations is associated with higher performance evaluations for teachers.

Faculty teaching performance is affected by the faculty's educational attainment

Table 4 presents the test of the significant relationship between the teachers' performance as affected by their educational attainment. As presented, educational attainment manifests highly significant results, as supported by the T-calculated value of (2.71) and F-calculated value of (7.36).

The finding implies that educational attainment is the best factor to attain very high level of teaching performance. The learnings acquired in every level of educational attainment can be used and applied in the teaching-learning process.

Relationship between the Teacher's Performance as Affected by their Educational Attainment

Table 4 presents the test of the significant relationship between the teachers' performance as affected by their educational attainment.

As presented, educational attainment manifested highly significant results, as supported by the T-Calculated value of (2.71) and F-Calculated value of (7.36).

Table 4. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Teacher's Performance as Affected by their Educational Attainment*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Regression Coefficients</i>	<i>T-Calculated Value</i>	<i>T-Probability (Level of Significance)</i>	<i>F-Calculated Value</i>	<i>F-Probability (Level of Significance)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Educational Attainment	0.9543	2.71	0.019	7.36	0.00	Highly Significant

The findings imply that educational attainment is the best factor to attain a very high level of teaching performance. The learnings acquired in every level of educational attainment can be used and applied in the teaching-learning process. Overall, these results suggest that higher educational attainment is strongly associated with improved teacher performance

It suggests that teachers with higher levels of education tend to perform noticeably better. This means that having extra qualifications—like advanced degrees or specialized certifications—can make a real difference, boosting their skills and overall teaching quality.

Research backs up the idea that teachers with higher education levels and specialized certifications tend to perform better in certain areas. For instance, Krimbill et al. (2022) found that teachers who earn advanced degrees can positively impact student performance, especially in middle school math. Similarly, the Midwestern Higher Education Compact reports that while the link between advanced degrees and teaching effectiveness can differ, there's solid evidence that such qualifications can boost teaching quality in subjects like early childhood education and reading. On top of that, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) highlighted that certified teachers often have stronger student outcomes than those without specialized training, emphasizing the importance of ongoing professional development and focused educational achievements.

Conclusions

Qualification is a special skill or type of experience or knowledge that qualifies someone for a specific job or activity. As a result, a teacher's qualification is a specific skill or type of experience or knowledge that someone possesses that qualifies him or her to teach. A teacher's qualifications could refer to all of the skills needed by a teacher to effectively teach. Formal education, experience, training, certificate/licensing, professional development ((de Vries et al., 2013) (Kola & Sunday, 2015) participation in professional organizations (Ebede, 2015), and teachers' empowerment (Avidov-Ungar et al., 2014) are some circumstances/avenues that teachers can acquire skills.

The faculty members in a private University in Cagayan de Oro possess the necessary knowledge, skills, competencies and essential qualifications to be regarded as competent teachers. The professional preparations, training, and support provided by the institution are sufficient for them to perform their expected role as effective classroom managers. Nevertheless, the faculty members must continue to pursue professional development to constantly remain competitive and keep abreast with the current trends and issues in education. Likewise, the institution must carry on its responsibility to support the professional growth of its teaching force.

To fulfill the school's vision and mission, collaboration between these two entities are necessary as these will advance the school not only locally but also globally.

The study highlights the significant role that teacher quality and teaching practices play at in a private university in Cagayan de Oro, making it clear that improvements in these areas are essential to boosting student success. The university may focus on identifying the qualities and methods that make teachers effective and work on enhancing those. Strengthening professional development programs is crucial because they have been proven to make teachers better at their jobs.

The university may also carefully evaluate which specific training approaches yield the most results. By creating a dedicated "teacher bureau," the university may systematically assess what training is needed and keep track of the quality of seminars, ensuring that the professional development offered is always up-to-date and meets high standards.

The university is also encouraged to expand its faculty scholarship program to motivate teachers to pursue further education, potentially easing the financial burden associated with advanced studies. Moreover, it suggests conducting a broader study that includes other higher education institutions to verify if the findings are consistent across different contexts.

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